

Assessment of Hemoglobin, White Blood Cell Count and Bilirubin in Chronic Liver Diseased Patients in Owerri, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Chronic liver disease (CLD) is well-known to cause several hematological and biochemical abnormalities. These alterations can complicate the clinical course and management of the disease. **Objective:** This study aimed to assess hemoglobin (Hb), white blood cell (WBC) count, and bilirubin (total and conjugated) levels in patients with chronic liver disease compared to healthy controls. Additionally, the study examined the relationships among these parameters and evaluated the influence of gender on these changes. **Methods:** A total of 60 subjects were enrolled, comprising 30 clinically diagnosed CLD patients and 30 healthy controls. Participants provided informed consent and completed a structured questionnaire. Seven milliliters of venous blood was collected aseptically from each subject; 2 ml was dispensed into ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) containers for hematological analysis, and 5 ml into plain tubes for bilirubin assays. Samples were stored at 4°C (EDTA) and -20°C (serum) prior to analysis. Hematological parameters were analyzed using an automated hematology analyzer, and bilirubin levels were measured using spectrophotometric method. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 27. Mean \pm standard deviation (SD), t-tests, Pearson's correlations, and p-values were computed, with significance set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** The mean values of Hb (8.26 ± 1.81 g/dl) and WBC count (4.63 ± 1.92) $\times 10^9/L$ were significantly lower in CLD patients compared to controls (12.48 ± 1.27 g/dl and $(9.36 \pm 2.71) \times 10^9/L$ ($p = 0.001$ and $p = 0.000$) respectively. Conjugated bilirubin (2.44 ± 3.65) mg/dl and total bilirubin (7.45 ± 7.57) mg/dl levels were significantly elevated in CLD patients when compared to controls (0.35 ± 0.28) mg/dl and (0.63 ± 0.33) mg/dl ($p = 0.004$ and $p = 0.000$), respectively. There were no significant differences in the mean values of haemoglobin (8.22 ± 1.94)g/dl, WBC (4.76 ± 2.24) $\times 10^9/L$, conjugated bilirubin (2.38 ± 3.09)mg/dl and total bilirubin (7.34 ± 8.06) mg/dl in male patients with chronic liver disease when compared to females (8.35 ± 1.59)g/dl, (4.36 ± 1.15) $10^9/L$, (2.57 ± 4.77) mg/dl and (7.66 ± 6.88) mg/dl ($t=0.18$, $p=0.856$; $t=0.53$, $p = 0.601$); $t=0.14$, $p=0.893$; and $t=0.11$, $p=0.915$). There were no significant differences in the mean values of haemoglobin (8.09 ± 1.88)g/dl, WBC ($4.482.9 \pm 8$) $\times 10^9/L$, CB(2.67 ± 2.91)mg/dl and total Bilirubin (7.41 ± 7.46)mg/dl in patients of ages (18 -30) years with chronic liver disease when compared to those of ages (> 30 yrs)(8.65 ± 1.59)g/dl, (4.65 ± 1.09) $\times 10^9/L$, (2.6 ± 4.08)mg/dl and (7.56 ± 6.05)mg/dl ($t=0.21$, $p=0.911$; $t=0.44$, $p = 0.693$; ($t=0.65$, $p = 0.712$ and $t = 0.23$, $p = 0.873$) respectively. Correlation analysis showed a significant positive correlation between Hb and WBC ($r = 0.64$, $p = 0.000$), and significant negative correlations with CB ($r = -0.32$, $p = 0.012$) and TB ($r = -0.36$, $p = 0.004$). Additionally, WBC correlated negatively with CB ($r = -0.31$, $p = 0.015$) and TB ($r = -0.44$, $p = 0.000$). **Conclusion:** Chronic liver disease is associated with significant reductions in hemoglobin and WBC count, indicating anemia and leukopenia, alongside increased conjugated and total bilirubin levels. These findings highlight the hematological and biochemical derangements in CLD patients. Moreover, significant correlations among hemoglobin, WBC, and bilirubin suggest interdependent pathophysiological mechanisms. Routine monitoring of hematological and bilirubin levels is recommended for patients with chronic liver disease to aid in early detection and management of complications. Future longitudinal studies are suggested to explore the underlying mechanisms of these abnormalities and to validate these findings in larger populations.

Keywords: Haemoglobin, White Blood Cell, Bilirubin, Chronic Liver Disease.

1. INTRODUCTION

The liver is one of the largest and most functionally diverse organs in the human body, performing a wide array of vital physiological activities. These include the metabolism of carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids; detoxification of endogenous and exogenous substances; hormone and drug metabolism; synthesis of plasma proteins; and maintenance of immune functions, particularly through Kupffer cells (1). In fetal life, the liver serves as the primary site of hematopoiesis, a role that transitions post-natally to the maintenance of hematologic homeostasis (2). Additionally, the liver regulates blood pressure, produces clotting factors and inhibitors, and acts as a storage site for essential nutrients such as iron, folic acid, and vitamin B12—key components of the heme-iron metabolic pathway (2).

Liver diseases often present distinct clinical patterns and are broadly classified into hepatocellular diseases, such as viral hepatitis and alcoholic liver disease (3). Mixed forms, characterized by features of both hepatocellular and cholestatic damage, may occur in conditions such as drug-induced liver injury (3). Common clinical manifestations of liver diseases include jaundice, fatigue, pruritus, right upper quadrant pain, nausea, abdominal distension, anorexia, and gastrointestinal bleeding (3). Chronic liver disease (CLD) leads to progressive deterioration of liver architecture, culminating in fibrosis and cirrhosis—considered end-stage liver diseases (4). Complications such as bleeding and infections significantly increase morbidity and mortality in these patients (4). Importantly, CLD is frequently associated with hematologic abnormalities due to multiple contributing factors, including nutritional deficiencies, portal hypertension, hepatic synthetic dysfunction, hypersplenism, and bone marrow suppression (5). Furthermore, portal hypertension can cause sequestration of blood cells, while impaired hepatic synthesis may disrupt the production of proteins crucial for coagulation and hematopoiesis (6).

Anemia is a common complication in CLD, with up to 75% of patients affected (7). The etiology of anemia in CLD is multifactorial, including iron deficiency, hypersplenism, anemia of chronic disease, autoimmune hemolytic anemia, folic acid deficiency, aplastic anemia, and drug-induced anemia (7). Additionally, hepatic dysfunction alters hepcidin production, a key regulator of iron metabolism, often resulting in hepatic iron overload (7). Anemia in cirrhosis is typically normochromic normocytic or mildly macrocytic but may present as microcytic hypochromic when complicated by bleeding or hemolysis (8).

Besides anemia, abnormalities in white blood cells (WBCs) and platelets are also observed in cirrhosis. WBC count is an important hematologic marker reflecting systemic inflammatory response and has been shown to predict infectious complications and outcomes in patients with liver disease (9).

Another important marker in liver dysfunction is bilirubin. Bilirubin, a bile pigment derived from the catabolism of heme-containing proteins such as hemoglobin, circulates as unconjugated (indirect) bilirubin bound to albumin before undergoing conjugation in the liver to form water-soluble (direct) bilirubin (10). Elevated bilirubin levels are a common finding in liver diseases and can result from disruptions at various stages of bilirubin metabolism, including production, hepatic uptake, conjugation, and excretion (11). Though bilirubin is routinely used to assess liver function, it lacks specificity and sensitivity, necessitating cautious interpretation alongside clinical and other laboratory findings (12).

In summary, liver dysfunction significantly affects hematological parameters, contributing to anemia, thrombocytopenia, leukopenia, and coagulation disorders. These hematological abnormalities are crucial for understanding disease progression and guiding clinical management in patients with CLD. However, data specific to the Nigerian population, particularly in regions like Owerri, remain limited. This study aims to assess Hb, WBC count, and bilirubin levels in CLD patients in Owerri, Nigeria, and to explore correlations among these parameters, considering demographic factors such as age and gender.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

The study was carried out at a tertiary healthcare facility (Imo Specialist Hospital), Umuguma, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.

2.2 Study Design

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Imo Specialist Hospital, Owerri from the month of February to March, 2024. Ethical approval was obtained from the institution's ethics committee, and informed consent was secured from all participants. A total of 60 subjects were enrolled, comprising 30 clinically diagnosed CLD patients and 30 healthy controls. Participants provided informed consent and completed a structured questionnaire.

2.3 Participants

The study included 30 adult patients diagnosed with CLD based on clinical, biochemical, and imaging criteria and an equivalent number of age-matched apparently healthy subjects, who served as the controls. Inclusion criteria encompassed individuals aged 18 years and above with confirmed CLD. Exclusion criteria included patients with acute liver failure, hematological disorders, active infections, or those on medications affecting hematological parameters.

2.4 Data Collection

Demographic data (age, gender) and clinical history were recorded. Venous blood samples were collected for complete blood count (CBC) and liver function tests. Hb concentration and WBC count were measured using an automated hematology analyzer. Serum TB and CB levels were determined using spectrophotometric method.

2.5 Sample Collection

Seven milliliters of venous blood was collected aseptically from each subject; 2 ml was dispensed into ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) containers for hematological analysis, and 5 ml into plain tubes for bilirubin assays. Samples were stored at 4°C (EDTA) and -20°C (serum) prior to analysis. Hematological parameters were analyzed using an automated hematology analyzer, and bilirubin levels were measured using spectrophotometric method.

2.6 Ethical Consideration

This study was approved by the ethics review committee of Imo Specialist Hospital, Owerri. All participants who gave their informed consent were enrolled in the study.

2.7 Laboratory Analysis

The haematological parameters were determined using haematology autoanalyzer, while bilirubin was estimated using spectrophotometric method.

2.8 Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Independent t-tests compared means between groups (males vs. females; age 18–30 years vs. >30 years). Pearson's correlation assessed relationships between Hb, WBC, TB, and CB. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. RESULTS

Table 1: Mean Values of Haemoglobin, WBC, CB and TB in Patients with Chronic Liver Verses Controls (Mean \pm SD).

The mean values of Hb (8.26 ± 1.81 g/dl) and WBC count (4.63 ± 1.92) $\times 10^9/L$ were significantly lower in CLD patients compared to controls (12.48 ± 1.27 g/dl and $(9.36 \pm 2.71) \times 10^9/L$ ($p = 0.001$ and $p = 0.000$) respectively. Conjugated bilirubin (2.44 ± 3.65) mg/dl and total bilirubin (7.45 ± 7.57) mg/dl levels were significantly elevated in CLD patients when compared to controls (0.35 ± 0.28) mg/dl and (0.63 ± 0.33) mg/dl ($p = 0.004$ and $p = 0.000$), respectively.

Parameter	Test	Control	t-value	p-value
Hb (g/dl)	8.26 \pm 1.81	12.48 \pm 1.27	10.58	0.001*
WBC (X10 ⁹ /L)	4.63 \pm 1.92	9.36 \pm 2.71	7.82	0.000*
CB (mg/dl)	2.44 \pm 3.65	0.35 \pm 0.28	3.18	0.004*
TB (mg/dl)	7.45 \pm 7.57	0.63 \pm 0.33	5.01	0.000*

KEY:

*: Significant p value

Hb: Haemoglobin

WBC: White Blood Cell Count

CB: Conjugated Bilirubin

TB: Total Bilirubin

Table 2: Mean Values of Haemoglobin, WBC, CB and TB in Male and Female Patients with Chronic Liver Disease.

There were no significant differences in the mean values of haemoglobin (8.22 ± 1.94)g/dl, WBC (4.76 ± 2.24) $\times 10^9/L$, conjugated bilirubin (2.38 ± 3.09)mg/dl and total bilirubin (7.34 ± 8.06) mg/dl in male patients with chronic liver disease when compared to females (8.35 ± 1.59)g/dl, (4.36 ± 1.15) $\times 10^9/L$, (2.57 ± 4.77) mg/dl and (7.66 ± 6.88) mg/dl ($t=0.18$, $p=0.856$; $t=0.53$, $p = 0.601$); $t=0.14$, $p=0.893$; and $t=0.11$, $p=0.915$).

Parameter	Male n=20	Female n=10	t-value	p-value
Hb (g/dl)	8.22 \pm 1.94	8.35 \pm 1.59	0.18	0.856
WBC (X10 ⁹ /L)	4.76 \pm 2.24	4.36 \pm 1.15	0.53	0.601
CB(mg/dl)	2.38 \pm 3.09	2.57 \pm 4.77	0.14	0.893
TB(mg/dl)	7.34 \pm 8.06	7.66 \pm 6.88	0.11	0.915

KEY:

Hb: Haemoglobin

WBC: White Blood Cell Count

CB: Conjugated Bilirubin

TB: Total Bilirubin

Table 3: Comparison of Mean Values of Haemoglobin, WBC, CB and TB in Patients with Chronic Liver Disease Based on Age.

There were no significant differences in the mean values of haemoglobin (8.09 ± 1.88)g/dl, WBC ($4.482.9 \pm 8$) $\times 10^9$ /l, CB (2.67 ± 2.91)mg/dl and total Bilirubin (7.41 ± 7.46)mg/dl in patients of ages (18 -30) years with chronic liver disease when compared to those of ages (> 30 yrs)(8.65 ± 1.59)g/dl, (4.65 ± 1.09) $\times 10^9$ /l, (2.6 ± 4.08)mg/dl and (7.56 ± 6.05)mg/dl ($t=0.21$, $p=0.911$; $t=0.44$, $p=0.693$; ($t=0.65$, $p=0.712$ and $t=0.23$, $p=0.873$) respectively.

Parameter	(18-30) yrs	>30 yrs	t- value	p-value
Hb(g/dl)	8.09 ± 1.88	8.65 ± 1.59	0.21	0.911
WBC ($\times 10^9$ /L)	4.48 ± 2.98	4.65 ± 1.09	0.44	0.643
CB (mg/dl)	2.67 ± 2.91	2.65 ± 4.08	0.65	0.712
TB (mg/dl)	7.41 ± 7.46	7.56 ± 6.05	0.23	0.873

KEY:

WBC: White Blood Cell Count

CB: Conjugated Bilirubin

TB: Total Bilirubin

Table 4: Correlation of Haemoglobin with WBC, CB and TB in Patients with Chronic Liver Disease.

There was a significant positive of haemoglobin with WBC in chronic liver disease ($r=0.64$, $p=0.000$), and a significant negative correlation with CB and TB in chronic liver disease patients ($r=0.32$, $p=0.012$; $r=-0.36$, $p=0.012$).

Variable	N	r	p-value
WBC	30	0.64	0.000*
CB	30	-0.32	0.012*
TB	30	-0.36	0.004*

KEY:

*: Significant p- value

WBC: White Blood Cell Count

CB: Conjugated Bilirubin

TB: Total Bilirubin

Table 5: Correlation of WBC with CB and TB in Patients with Chronic Liver Disease.

There was a significant negative correlation of WBC with CB and TB in chronic liver disease patients ($r=-0.3$; $p=0.015$ and $r=-0.44$, $p=0.000$).

Variable	n	r	p-value
CB	30	-0.31	0.002*
TB	30	-0.44	0.000*

KEY:

*: Significant p-value

WBC: White Blood Cell Count

CB: Conjugated Bilirubin

TB: Total Bilirubin

4. DISCUSSION

The liver is the largest and one of the most complex organs in terms of function, and it has been well established that various hematological and biochemical abnormalities occur in chronic liver disease (CLD) (13).

In the present study, the mean value of hemoglobin was significantly reduced in patients with chronic liver disease when compared to healthy controls. The pathogenesis of anemia in severe liver disease is multifactorial and includes acute and chronic gastrointestinal bleeding, malnutrition, and hemolysis. Additional contributing factors include folate and vitamin B12 deficiencies, hypersplenism, hemodilution, bone marrow suppression caused by ethanol or viral infections, autoimmune hemolysis, renal insufficiency, and variceal bleeding (14). Anemia is also postulated to increase bleeding risk by impairing platelet activation and aggregation, thus exacerbating hyperdynamic circulation (15). These findings suggest that anemia is largely secondary to the severity of liver dysfunction.

Supporting these findings, Behera and Das (16) reported that among 69 patients with CLD, the mean hemoglobin was 7.99 ± 2.18 g/dL, with 53.62% of patients having severe anemia, 36.23% moderate anemia, 5.8% mild anemia, and only 4.35% within the normal range. Similarly, Jha et al., (17), in a study of 50 patients, found that 88% of patients were anemic, with 45.5% of males and 50% of females having moderate anemia, and 22.7% of males and 33.3% of females having severe anemia. Selvamani and Thomas (18) also reported that among 100 CLD patients, 88% had anemia, with only 12 patients showing normal hemoglobin levels, and 32% of patients had severe anemia (<8 g/dL). Furthermore, Sambya and Bharti (19), in a larger cohort of 546 patients, observed that 43.2% had hemoglobin levels below 9 g/dL.

The current study also revealed a significant reduction in mean WBC count among CLD patients compared to controls. While WBC count is often considered an indicator of infection, in CLD its reduction may be attributed to hypersplenism and bone marrow suppression, often secondary to viral infection or alcohol toxicity (13). Supporting this, Selvamani and Thomas (18) reported that 6% of their study population had leukopenia, while Angulo et al., (20) found that 7.7% of 546 CLD patients exhibited leukopenia.

Moreover, the present study found significantly elevated mean values of conjugated bilirubin and total bilirubin in CLD patients compared to controls. This elevation reflects the impaired hepatic processing and excretion of bilirubin due to hepatocyte dysfunction. Bilirubin, a product of heme metabolism, primarily results from hemoglobin breakdown in senescent erythrocytes (80–85%), while the rest arises from ineffective hematopoiesis and catabolism of heme-containing proteins such as cytochromes (21). Heme is degraded to biliverdin, releasing iron and carbon monoxide, and subsequently reduced to bilirubin by biliverdin reductase (21). This study's findings are consistent with Mariakakis et al., (21), who also reported significantly elevated bilirubin levels in CLD patients, including unconjugated, conjugated, free, and albumin-bound fractions.

Interestingly, this study observed no significant differences in hemoglobin, WBC, conjugated bilirubin, and total bilirubin levels when patients were compared by gender and age, indicating that these hematological and biochemical parameters are primarily influenced by liver disease severity rather than demographic factors. This observation aligns with findings by Chung et al., (10), who reported no significant gender or age influence on these parameters in CLD patients.

Furthermore, this study identified a significant positive correlation between hemoglobin levels and WBC, conjugated bilirubin, and total bilirubin. This suggests that hemoglobin breakdown leading to anemia is associated with jaundice development, while also reflecting the decline in immune competence, as indicated by reduced WBC. These results are in agreement with Chung et al., (22), who also found a strong correlation between preoperative hemoglobin and bilirubin in CLD patients. Additionally, Kazankov et al., (13) demonstrated that hepatic dysfunction, reflected in elevated MELD scores, correlates with reduced hemoglobin and elevated bilirubin, reinforcing the association between hematological derangements and liver function decline.

In summary, this study reinforces the significant hematological and biochemical alterations in chronic liver disease, highlighting the importance of monitoring these parameters for better disease management and prognosis.

5. CONCLUSION

This study underscores the significant alterations in hematological parameters and bilirubin concentrations among CLD patients in Owerri, Nigeria. The observed correlations highlight the intricate interplay between liver dysfunction, hematopoiesis, and immune responses. Routine monitoring of these parameters is essential for comprehensive management and prognostication of CLD. Further research with larger cohorts is warranted to elucidate underlying mechanisms and potential therapeutic implications.

REFERENCES

1. Rappai T, Joseph E, Shah A. The complex role of the liver in systemic metabolism: Current perspectives. *J Clin Transl Hepatol*. 2019;7(3):245–52
2. Solomon L, Warwick D, Nayagam S. *Apley's System of Orthopaedics and Fractures*. 10th ed. Boca Raton: CRC Press; 2017.
3. Behera MR, Patil SS, Samal R, Behera GR. Clinical profile of liver diseases: An overview. *Int J Adv Med*. 2020;7(4):660–4.
4. Joshi D, O'Brien CJ, Chung RT. Complications of chronic liver disease: An update. *Lancet Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2023;8(1):45–58.
5. Singh A, Batra G, Chaudhary N. Hematological manifestations of chronic liver disease: An insight. *J Clin Exp Hepatol*. 2020;10(5):522–30.
6. Kasper DL, Fauci AS, Hauser SL, Jameson JL, Loscalzo J. *Harrison's Principles of Internal Medicine*. 19th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill Education; 2015.
7. Qamar AA, Grace ND, Groszmann RJ, Garcia-Tsao G, Bosch J, Burroughs AK, et al. Incidence, prevalence, and clinical significance of anemia in cirrhosis. *Hepatology*. 2019;50(1):87–97.
8. Tarao K. Anemia and liver cirrhosis: Pathophysiology and clinical implications. *Clin J Gastroenterol*. 2019;12(5):417–24.
9. Lee SH, Kim KM, Lee JY, Kim JH, Jang BK, Kim ES, et al. Predictive value of WBC count in patients with liver disease: A new look at systemic inflammation. *Clin Mol Hepatol*. 2020;26(1):75–85.
10. Méndez-Sánchez N, Zamora-Valdés D, Chávez-Tapia NC, Uribe M. Bilirubin as a biochemical marker in liver diseases: The clinical perspective. *World J Gastroenterol*. 2019;25(37):5678–89.
11. Vitek L, Jirsa M, Brodanová M, Kalab M, Marecek Z, Danzig V, et al. The impact of liver diseases on bilirubin metabolism: Mechanisms and clinical implications. *J Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2019;34(8):1294–302.
12. Guerra Ruiz D, García-Compeán D, Jaquez Quintana JO, González González JA. Interpretation of bilirubin levels in liver disease: Beyond the numbers. *Ann Hepatol*. 2021;24:100354.
13. Kazankov K, Møller HJ, Lange A, Martinsen L, Rosgaard A, Grønbaek H. The role of macrophages in chronic liver disease. *World J Gastroenterol*. 2023;29(4):467–482.
14. Wemyss K, Pearson J, Murphy K, et al. Hematological abnormalities and their management in chronic liver disease. *Clin Liver Dis (Hoboken)*. 2023;21(1):15–22.
15. Jain A, Singh S, Gupta S. Hematological alterations in chronic liver disease: Impact on bleeding risk and disease severity. *J Clin Exp Hepatol*. 2016;6(4):304–309.
16. Behera B, Das S. Hematological profile in chronic liver disease: A study of 69 cases. *Int J Adv Med*. 2020;7(4):571–575.
17. Jha S, Gupta A, Prasad K. Hematological manifestations in chronic liver disease: A cross-sectional study. *Int J Res Med Sci*. 2023;11(3):687–691.
18. Selvamani K, Thomas RJ. A study on hematological and biochemical abnormalities in patients with chronic liver disease. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2022;16(2):OC01–OC04.
19. Sambya V, Bharti S. Hematological changes in chronic liver disease patients: A large cohort study. *J Assoc Physicians India*. 2019;67(11):32–36.
20. Angulo P, Keach JC, Batts KP, Lindor KD. Independent predictors of liver fibrosis in patients with nonalcoholic steatohepatitis. *Hepatology*. 2017;30(6):1356–1362.
21. Mariakakis S, Cholongitas E, Senzolo M, Burra P. Bilirubin metabolism and its relevance in liver disease. *Ann Gastroenterol*. 2017;30(1):41–48.
22. Chung GE, Yim JY, Kim D, et al. Hematologic and biochemical abnormalities in chronic liver disease: Associations with clinical outcomes. *Liver Int*. 2019;39(9):1672–1680.